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Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition In Business Education Programme: A Tool for Graduates Employability In An Unstable Economy

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ABSTRACT

This paper examined entrepreneurial skills acquisition through Business Education as a tool for self-employability amongst graduates in Rivers State. The entrepreneurial skills that are acquired in Business Education programme includes; marketing skills, accounting skills and office management and technology skills. Marketing skills enables graduates to know how to promote products and brands. Accounting skills equips individuals with the skills that are required for accessing and managing financial resources of a business. While office management and technology skills equips individuals with the skills needed to effectively manage an office and the relevant information available in the office setting. Marketing skills focuses on the stimulation of demands from business customers while office management technology skills deal with management of office space and facilities while information and communication technology skills deals with the harnessing of available and innovative information and communication technologies (software and hardware) to improve communication and information management in a business organization. It was concluded in this paper that entrepreneurial skills in Business Education plays significant roles in enabling graduates to be independent and self-reliant and it was suggested that the Entrepreneurial skills taught in Business Education should be adequately taught in a manner that it will enable graduates to be self-reliant.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneurial skills, Business Education.

INTRODUCTION

Education is the spring board to socio-economic growth and development of every nation which prepares an individual to live in a dynamic or constantly changing society and contribute to such changes and constantly advance the survival, growth and development of the society. Education is a veritable means of developing individuals to become skillful, knowledgeable, experienced, resourceful and able to contribute towards the development of the nation. The philosophy of the current system of education is expressed in terms of national education goals includes; acquisition of appropriate skills and development of mental, physical and social abilities and competencies as equipment for the individual to be able to live in and contribute to the development of his society (Federal republic of Nigeria, 2013). This advocates the need for the type of education that will enable the individual to acquire general education on the one hand and on the other hand be technically and economically productive.

The rate of graduate unemployment in Nigeria has continuously been on the high side. Despite the enormous endowment of the country with human and natural resources, the problem appears to persist. While graduate unemployment remains an endemic problem in Nigeria, the situation is not peculiar to only Nigeria. It is a situation that is common to many nations (Olayinka, 2010). In fact, the problem of graduate unemployment is considered a long standing global phenomenon. Graduates refers to persons who have successfully completed their tertiary education programme and have been duly certified as been found worthy in character and learning. This brings to light the need for Entrepreneurial skills through Entrepreneurship Education.

Over the years entrepreneurship has been conceptualized by different authors from different perspectives. Entrepreneurship is derived from the French word “entreprendre” meaning to undertake”. Entrepreneurship is the willingness and ability of an individual to seek for investment opportunities, to establish and to run an enterprise successfully (Suleiman, 2006). Accordingly, Nwangwu (2006) opined that entrepreneurship is the willingness and the ability of an individual or a firm or an organization to identify an environmental change and exploit such an opportunity to produce goods and services for public consumption. Long (2010) focused on the opportunistic elements of entrepreneurship, which defines the concept based on pursuit and exploitation of business opportunities. Thus, entrepreneurship is commonly defined as the process of creating a business, characteristics of seeking opportunities, taking risks beyond security and having the tenacity to push an idea through to reality combined into special perspectives that permeate entrepreneurs.

Amaewhule (2014) sees entrepreneurship as the driving force for economic development and transformation which provides opportunity for students to effectively contribute to the economic development of the nation. Idomeh, Anabor and Okoli (2009) asserted that the growing importance of the role of entrepreneurs in a country’s economic growth and development has stirred up both developed and developing countries to formulate policies that would promote its development in their economy hence, the federal government of Nigeria through the National Universities Commission (NUC) has made entrepreneurship a compulsory requirement for graduation for all programmes in Nigerian universities. Entrepreneurship is associated with a number of activities including the following:

i The ability to create and build something from nothing, the ability of having a vision matched with focus and determination of building an enterprise.

ii. The skill for seeing an opportunity where others fail to do so; the ability to build a working team to complement your own talents and efforts.

iii. The ability to aggregate, marshal and control resources judiciously; the willingness and ability of innovativeness and creativity

iv. The willingness to undertake personal and financial risks; the ability to engage in activities despite all odds and in fact surmounting these odds and possibly turn them into your own favours.

Thus, entrepreneurship is more than being smart and entails the possession of key skills and talents; innovativeness and the combination and usage of all these together with an entrepreneurship spirit. Ubulom and Enyoghasim (2012) classified entrepreneurship into these four categories; basic production, processing, distribution and services.

a. Basic Production: this includes farming, poultry, fishery, forestry, animal husbandry etcetera. A veterinary medical doctor with an entrepreneurial skill can set up a piggery or goatry while a botanist can go for tree plantation and agriculturist can go for growing of yam, cassava, wheat, beans, potato, and plantain etcetera.

b. Processing: this includes manufacturing, construction, food processing, publishing and printing. The home economist can manufacture soap; bake different kinds of food from flour, knit sweater and cardigan. The educationist can open a model private commercial school.

c. Distribution: this includes wholesale and retail trading, advertising, transportation and some forms of communication businesses. Individuals with developed entrepreneurial skills can go into selling of one commodity or the other, open supermarkets, business Centre’s etcetera.

d. Services: this includes finance, insurance, professional services such as secretarial and other reprographic functions.

When an individual has through series of training in Entrepreneurship education, it is expected that the person ought to practice what he or she has been taught during Entrepreneurial training thereby making the person an Entrepreneur.

An Entrepreneur is one who possesses the above mentioned abilities and activates them in establishing a venture for the purpose of profit maximization. Fitriati and Hermiati (2010) asserted that an entrepreneur is one who undertakes innovations, finances and displays business in an effort to transform innovations into economic goods. Amaewhule (2014) describes the entrepreneur as someone who visualizes business opportunities and who uses available resources to fill the gap arising from such opportunities in order to make profit. Thus, an entrepreneur is both an agent of change and risk bearer in business who organizes work, makes final decisions, finds customers to ensure survival of the business enterprise and handles other diverse activities at the same time. Oduma (2012) identifies a successful entrepreneur as an individual who possess the characteristics such as technical competence, risk taking, high initiative and good judgment, intelligence to analyze and solve problem areas, leadership qualities, confidence, positive attitude, and high level of energy, creativeness, honesty, integrity, emotional stability and fairness.

Nwabufo (2013) posited some of the positive characteristics of an entrepreneur to include: self-confidence, risk taking, task (result) orientation, drive and energy, leadership, creativity, initiative, positive aggression, trust and honesty, delegation of authority, loyalty and good planner and organizer. Okojie (2009) in his study states that the entrepreneur is believed to possess some characteristics which are commonly associated with entrepreneurs. These characteristics differ from one entrepreneur to another and they include; dynamism, self- confidence, hard work, courage, leadership, risk taking, innovation, and goal setting among others.

i. Dynamism: this is the drive or urges that keeps an entrepreneur going. An entrepreneur should be very ambitious, have a strong personality and energy to forge ahead in business.

ii. Self-confidence: this gives an entrepreneur a strong belief in his business, and show to others that he means business. The entrepreneurs do not ask questions whether they can succeed or whether they are worthy of success because they are confident with the knowledge that their business will succeed.

iii. Hard work: a typical entrepreneur work round the clock to ensure growth and stability of the business enterprise as he/she makes no distinction between office private and office hours. This is an indispensable ingredient of success in entrepreneurship.

iv. Courage: this is a quality that makes an entrepreneur to forge ahead in spite of setbacks, challenges, risks, difficulties and frustrations associated with business venture or entrepreneurship business.

v. Leadership: this is a quality of an entrepreneur that incites him to initiate actions, organize, control, guide, inspire and motivate others for business.

vi. Risk taking: this is the readiness to take a chance in a situation of uncertainty. Entrepreneurs know that success depends on care and therefore does not gamble but take calculated risk.

vii. Innovation: this is the ability to discover new ideas, device or methods, ways and opportunities or better solution that meet new requirement or existing market needs.

viii. Goal setting: this is the ability of an entrepreneur to set goals and target for themselves, have mission, and a drive to reach the mark. It is the goal setting strategy that makes the entrepreneur to combine other important entrepreneurial traits and challenge his abilities, ideas, ambition and aspirations to the greatest advantage. An entrepreneur is any person who perceives business opportunities, initiates the business and applies scarce resources rationally and in a most beneficial manner to guarantee profits and survival of the business venture. Therefore, entrepreneurship can only be achieved through effective entrepreneurship education that gives learners access to skills and knowledge required to be entrepreneurs. Through entrepreneurship education, graduates especially those of Business Education are equipped to find new methods of doing things and enabled to be own bosses and job “creators” rather than job “seekers”. Education is considered as one of the effective tools for human capital and societal

development, because no nation can attain an appreciable level of development beyond the level of her education (Adekola & Kumbe, 2012). Education is the process of acquiring knowledge, special skills and experiences by an individual for effective conquering and adaptation to his environment.

Entrepreneurship Education and Skills Acquisition

Entrepreneurship education seeks to provide students with skills, knowledge and motivation, as well as to effect attitudinal changes, necessary to encourage self-reliance through involvement in entrepreneurial activities (Abiodun, 2017). Through entrepreneurial education, young people learn organizational skills, time management, and leadership involvement in entrepreneurial activities. Students are therefore exposed to basic entrepreneurial skills such as accounting, managerial, marketing, office management, as well as information and technology in order to become good entrepreneurs on graduation. The outlined indicate an individual's entrepreneurial competence that can determine his/her intention to start a business. According to Schmitt-Rodermund as cited in Zhengxia Peng, Genshu Lu and Hui Kang (2012), students' entrepreneurial competences refer to their leadership, curiosity and entrepreneurial skills which are influenced by personality traits.

Entrepreneurial Skills and Employability Skills

Skills are practical knowledge that are gained on how to carry out specific tasks or duties. Sometimes, skills are seen as a means to an end; not an end in itself. The skills that are associated with Entrepreneurship Education are almost universal to different industries. This is because every industry offers some level of opportunities potential investors. Students who offer Entrepreneurship Education are not limited to any sector. They can venture into any sector depending on their interest. Irrespective of the industry, the goals of every business firm include, to maximize resources, improve service delivery and customer satisfaction, and optimize business profit (Alberti & Poli, 2004). The core skills that are needed for the achievement of business goals, in almost all forms of business ventures are known as business management skills or entrepreneurial skills.

Entrepreneurial skills are highly technical skills that are needed to manage and successfully operate or run ones' venture (Sule, 2013). Each of the entrepreneurial skill focuses only on one of the aspects of the life of a business. The entrepreneurial skill-set therefore technically covers all the different important aspects of the life of a business. It is through entrepreneurial education that students are exposed to basic knowledge of the different entrepreneurial skills (Sule 2013).

Employability skills are the skills needed by individuals to function effectively and efficiently in the world of work either as an employee or an employer of labor. The employability skills of a job seeker will go a long way in determining the relative standing of the individual in the labor market.

Employability incorporates the dual aspects of supply and demand of labor to show that advancing one's position in the labor market by gaining credentials is partially dependent on structural factors outside the individual's control. Brown and Hesketh (2014) stressed that there is a clear mismatch between individual's expectations of employability and the realities posed by the labor market. This was what informed the classification of job seekers by Brown and Hesketh into two and they are: purist and players. The authors described the purists as those that believe in merit in getting their desired jobs because they have the requirements for the job. On the other hand, the players adopt any means possible to secure their desired jobs either by 'hook or crook' (that is, either legally or illegally). With the recent development in this part of the world, the players tend to thrive owing to the limited job opportunities.

The lack of basic knowledge of the application of entrepreneurial skills may impede communication and cooperation between a business owner (entrepreneur) and a hired expert of one or more of the aspects of entrepreneurial skills. The dearth of many small and medium scales has been linked to entrepreneurial skills amongst affected business owners (Ndu, 2016). The need for graduates to possess basic entrepreneurial skills cannot be overemphasized. This perhaps justifies the need for Entrepreneurial Education to amongst others, inculcate entrepreneurial skills into students offering Entrepreneurial Education in universities. Entrepreneurial skills include; accounting skills, managerial skills, marketing skills, office management technology skills, and information and communication technology skills (Adekola & Kumbe, 2012).

Accounting skills are required for accessing and managing financial resources of a business, managerial skills deals with the management of human and other business resources in other to ensure their optimization and smooth coordination of the different aspects of the business life, marketing skills focuses on the stimulation of demands from business customers while office management technology skills deals with management of office space and facilities while information and communication technology skills deals with the harnessing of available and innovative information and communication technologies (software and hardware) to improve communication and information management in a business organization. Entrepreneurial skills are uniquely different. However, there is need to ensure that there is linkage or interconnection of the entrepreneurial skills. This is because businesses are systems with independent but interdependent parts (Okorie, 2009). The management of finance in a business cannot be done in isolation of management of human resources or information neither can office management be done without consideration to management of finance.

The entrepreneurial skills inculcated into students through Entrepreneurship Education is supposed to inspire the students to engage in continuous learning in order to effectively manage their businesses through the application of requisite entrepreneurial skills.

Amahi (2016) opined that the skills acquired in any of the functional areas of business related programme promotes training in entrepreneurship as well as equip Graduates with requisite potentials to establish and run small businesses on their own. According to Ademiluyi (2017), entrepreneurship skills are simply business skills which individuals acquire to enable them effectively function in the turbulent business environment as an entrepreneur or self-employed. Akinola (2011) pointed out that it takes special skills to succeed as an entrepreneur most especially the female folks. The future of the female entrepreneurs becomes worrisome due to gender-related discriminations prevalent in developing countries like Nigeria inclusive (Roomi & Parrot, 2008; May, 2007).

Another aspect of Entrepreneurial skill is communication skill. Communication is a competence that can be regarded as the ability to interact appropriately and effectively with others (Chen & Starosta, 2010). Communication, which is a vital skill for all professions, is at the core of business venture operation in terms of Business-client relationships (Dua, 2015).

Ilesanmi (2010) mentioned what an entrepreneur requires for effective communication skills to include how communication process helps the entrepreneur effect the managerial functions of planning, organizing, staffing, influencing, interacting, controlling, and coordinating. In terms of information flow within an organization, it moves in different directions depending on the employee hierarchy within the organization. In the contemporary business setting, information flows faster than ever before. This is required since the advent of the internet era where such mediums, both for social and business are highly employed in business organizations. Such media platforms include Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, WhatsApp, Google+, LinkedIn, YouTube, among others. Information needs to flow faster now than ever before. Slightest shortage in information flow could be very costly. In present-day business world, information must flow uninterruptedly as information stoppage on a fast-moving production line can cause a huge damage in terms of output as well as loss of customer goodwill.

Entrepreneurial Skills Acquired In Business Education Programme

Business Education programme equips individuals with various entrepreneurial skills such as marketing skills, accounting skills and office management skills. Marketing skills as part of Entrepreneurial skills equips one with the abilities and techniques needed to interact with potential buyers in order to stimulate demand for goods and services thereby enabling a graduate to be a good marketer of personal product or an organization's product (Fitriati, & Hermiati, 2010). Marketing skills deals more with the use of various methods and technologies for effective business communication (Fitriati, & Hermiati, 2010). The goal of such communication as part of Entrepreneurial skill is to stimulate and increase product sales and customer relation thereby making graduates good customer service officers in their businesses or in an organization. Almost all business enterprise is concerned with the sales of goods and services. The higher the sales figures, the higher the total revenue generated by the business. Marketing is a critical aspect of

business as it directly is concerned with achieving desired sales performance. The entrepreneur who begins a small and medium scale firm may not have the resources to hire a trained and certified marketer for his/her products. This constrained should not be responsible for zero sales in the business.

A trained entrepreneur is expected to possess basic knowledge, skills and competence in product marketing. This implies that an entrepreneur should have basic knowledge of what to do (what strategy or technology to use) in order to create awareness of his/her product and convince potential buyers to patronize the business. In an open market, competitiveness prevails (Fitriati, & Hermiati, 2010). Marketing skills will enable entrepreneurs to gain some level of competitive advantage and favourable share of the existing and potential market. Office management skill is another essential entrepreneurial skill. This is because business don't operate in vacuum. Businesses are sited in places known as offices. A business office may be small, large, closed or open. No matter what type of office used for running a business, they need to ensure proper housekeeping for smooth operations in the office cannot be overemphasized. An office is like any room. Its space is limited and therefore needs to be planned and managed.

Items in it should be worth any space allocated to them and users should find the space clean, safe and conducive for various activities and purposes. The keyword for office management skill is housekeeping' (Obasi, 2017). A lot of skill is need for effective housekeeping in a limited office space. Such skills include planning, mapping, organizing and others. Office management skills are required for effective office management. Office management skills refer to skills that are needed for day-to-day office housekeeping, interaction and business transactions. The aesthetical outlook of an office depends on the level of office management skills possessed by the business owner. Man-hour loss arising from too frequent movement, accidents and searching for items are eradicated through the use of office management skills (Adindu, 2017). An entrepreneur needs office management skill to be able to arrange all items in the office in a way that they can be identified, stored and retrieved with ease and less time.

A decently arranged office appears to enhance the morale of the business owner as well as customer satisfaction. Planning and office mapping are essential elements of office management skill. Everything in an office should be placed and arranged where they are best fitted. Although an entrepreneur may need to hire a person trained and certified in office management as a staff or consultant, it is cost effective for small and medium scale business owners to harness the office management skills that were inculcated into them during their Business Education/entrepreneurship training programmes. Information and communication technology skill is also very crucial entrepreneurial skill. No business can be successfully run without the practice of gathering, classifying, storing and retrieving information. Irrespective of the size of a business, there is need for effective communication of useful information (Abdulazeez, 2016).

The ability to use computerized technology to carry-out the process of gathering, classification and organization, storage and retrieval of useful information within a business framework is known as 'information and communication technology skill'. There are several hardware and software gadgets/applications that are designed to enhance the execution of almost all kinds of business activities and operations. The use of computerized hardware and software gadgets/applications requires competences ranging from simple to complex. An entrepreneur needs to possess basic simple competences for utilizing simple and generic computerized hardware and software gadgets/applications for day-to-day running of business and management of business information/communication. The emergence of internet and social media has offered huge opportunities for businesses to source, enrich and exchange useful information with their target audience (Abdulazeez, 2016). Unfortunately, most tertiary institutions in Nigeria that have Entrepreneurship programme lack the requisite computer laboratory, model office technologies or internet centers needed to expose Business Education students to technology utilization (Ordu and Uduak,2012). This in turn hampers students' ability to acquire digital communication skill as part of the Entrepreneurial skills needed to be an effective Entrepreneurs.

CONCLUSION

It was concluded in this paper that entrepreneurial skills in Business Education plays significant roles in enabling graduates to be independent and self-reliant. These skills enable them to be job creators and employers of labour in today's world where unemployment is on the increase.

SUGGESTIONS

The following suggestion were made by the researcher:

1. The Entrepreneurial skills taught in Business Education should be adequately taught in a manner that it will enable graduates to be self-reliant.
2. More emphasis should be laid on enabling students to be entrepreneurial in nature so as to create jobs for themselves and others.
3. Entrepreneurial skill acquisition programmes in Business Education should be geared towards the empowerment of its graduates to function effectively in today's world.

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